

Biofilm monitoring through the detection of cyclic diguanosine-monophosphate with an easy-to-use electrochemical sensor

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Biofilm detection
cdGMP
Nanomaterials
Sensors
Biofilm evolution detection, *Escherichia Coli*
Pseudomonas aeruginosa
Proteus vulgaris

ABSTRACT

The identification and monitoring of biofilm is of utmost importance because it ensures the survival of bacteria in a variety of environments, such as nature, medical indwelling devices, hospital surfaces, or the food industry. Here, we describe the novel application of a screen-printed electrode modified with nanomaterials for the *in situ* detection of bacterial biofilm. This approach enables simple, rapid, and highly sensitive and selective electrochemical detection of cyclic diguanosine-monophosphate (cdGMP). The best electrochemical signal of cdGMP was obtained after testing several electrode materials and screen-printed electrodes modified with different nanomaterials, different electrolyte solutions, pH, and electrochemical technique parameters. Using the anodic peak of the cdGMP on screen-printed electrodes modified with carbon nanotubes (CNT-SPE), the sensor showed excellent sensitivity, with a 25 nM–1 μM linear range, and a limit of detection of 15 nM. The sensor allowed the selective detection of cdGMP, with low interference from other molecules and was successfully applied to real sample analyses (laboratory biofilm produced by various bacterial species over distinct time intervals).

1. Introduction

The ability of bacteria to form biofilm and develop resistance to conventional antibiotics and detergents presents significant clinical and scientific challenges. The biofilm consists of a structured bacterial community encased tightly in an extracellular matrix, exhibiting a complex architecture formed by self-produced polymeric substances. Bacteria growing in the biofilm demonstrate resilience across a variety of natural, clinical, or industrial environments, including medical indwelling devices, different surfaces in hospitals, water supply systems, and the food industry. Many pathogenic bacteria utilize biofilms to survive in challenging external conditions, waiting for a suitable host. For instance, *Vibrio cholera* forms biofilms in diverse aquatic environments and promptly establishes intestinal colonization upon ingestion by the mammalian host [1–3].

The biofilms-associated infections are predominantly related to indwelling devices (catheters, prosthetic joints), as well as valves of endocarditis, open wounds, or dental materials [1]. An important aspect is that microbial biofilms can escape the host's immune system, with the majority of chronic infections being linked to biofilm formation [2,3].

Furthermore, various sectors of the food industry, including poultry, dairy, aquaculture, or ready-to-eat confront challenges posed by biofilm-producing microorganisms, resulting in food spoilage, disease outbreaks, and finally deaths [2,3]. The consumption of contaminated foodstuffs not only compromises the quality of life, but also imposes important economic repercussions. Food and food processing settings represent an ideal environment for biofilm formation, making cross-contamination associated with raw and processed food through contact surfaces, an important risk factor for bacterial infections in humans. Incidents like food-borne outbreaks after consuming salads contaminated with pathogenic bacteria (e.g., *Escherichia coli* O157: H7) exemplify this matter [1–3]. A significant concern associated with cross-contamination is the prolonged viability of bacteria on food surfaces, attributed to biofilm formation. Within biofilms, bacteria exhibit enhanced resistance, being up to 1000 times more protected than their planktonic counterparts from antibiotics, detergents, environmental stress, and the host's immune system and can persist on both biotic and abiotic surfaces [1–4]. Recognizing the escalating concerns about bacterial biofilms in water settings and antibiotic resistance, the World Health Organization (WHO) has emphasized the importance of

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innovative, sensitive biofilm characterization strategies [5]. Within this context, there is an urgent need for new, advanced sensing approaches to identify and monitor biofilm formation.

Biofilm formation is a complex, sequential process encompassing six stages: i) initial reversible attachment, ii) irreversible attachment, iii) microcolonies formation in young biofilms, iv) maturation stage leading to a mature biofilm structure, v) dispersal phase characterized by matrix cavity formation and bacterial dispersion, and vi) recolonization of other surfaces [2,4]. Several mechanisms and compounds contribute to biofilm formation. For instance, quorum sensing (QS), a population-dependent regulatory mechanism mediated by self-secreted molecules called auto-inducers (AI), plays a pivotal role in virulence and biofilm formation. Another very important mechanism in the formation of biofilm, especially in Gram-negative bacteria, is cyclic diguanosine-monophosphate (cdGMP) regulation [1,2,4]. CdGMP serves as a ubiquitous second messenger in bacteria, orchestrating key bacterial processes [6]. One of the most important roles in the biofilm formation of this signaling molecule is the post-translational activation of the synthase enzymes involved in the synthesis of common biofilm matrix components, such as cellulose, alginate, Pel, and other polysaccharides [7].

The detection and characterization of the bacterial biofilm pose significant challenges and many studies have focused on this topic. Microscopy techniques, including scanning electron microscopy (SEM), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), or atomic force microscopy (AFM) are usually used for biofilm investigations. While these methods have shown important progress in recent years, they are primarily employed in the ultrastructural characterization of the biofilm rather than in the detection of its formation [5,8,9]. Another approach to identifying biofilm formation is the detection of QS molecules [10–15], but these molecules are involved especially in the initial stages of biofilm formation, without providing important information related to the stage of evolution of the biofilm. Since cdGMP is involved in all stages of biofilm formation [4], the detection of this molecule can provide valuable information regarding the presence of biofilm and the developmental phase, elucidating bacterial adaptive strategies and guiding intervention strategies in clinical and industrial contexts. Several methods for detecting cdGMP have been reported, such as fluorescent methods [5,16,17] or biosensors [18], but the chromatographic methods remain the gold standard [4,6,19–21]. Although these methods demonstrate effective analytical performance, they are accompanied by certain limitations. These include elaborate protocols for extraction and isolation, costly laboratory instruments and reagents, long analysis time, the use of expensive and polluting solvents, and a limitation in facilitating decentralized analyses [4,12,15,19].

Fortunately, the electrochemical sensors overcome these limitations and represent a viable alternative for simple and sensitive detection of small molecules even in complex matrices, such as biofilm. They offer several advantages, including biocompatibility, cost-effectiveness, quick analytical response, and high sensitivity and selectivity [4,5]. Additionally, screen-printed electrodes (SPEs) offer the possibility of miniaturization and have revolutionized field-based analyte detection across various biological samples. They offer advantages like mass production, low cost, single-use (eliminating the problems associated with electrode fouling), ease of use, minimal sample requirements, and short analysis time [22,23]. Another advantage of SPEs is the possibility of modification with nanomaterials, such as graphene (GPH), carbon nanotubes (CNT), and metallic nanoparticles (NPs). These nanomaterials are highly favored in electrochemical platform development due to their inherent characteristics, including expansive surface area, excellent conductivity, biocompatibility, ease of modification, and functionalization capabilities [24].

In this study, a novel, fast, easy-to-use, and sensitive method for the detection of cdGMP was developed, employing for the first time the peak obtained by its electrochemical oxidation using commercially available SPE modified with CNT (CNT-SPE). The sensor underwent optimization

concerning electrode surface, electrolyte, pH, and electrochemical parameters. The optimized sensor facilitated the robust and selective detection of cdGMP with a very low limit of detection (LOD = 15 nM), demonstrating utility in detecting the analyte in the complex matrix of the biofilm cultivated in the laboratory from three distinct bacterial strains (*Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Proteus vulgaris*). Thereby the developed sensor serves as a valuable tool for the identification of bacterial biofilm on different contaminated surfaces and holds applicability in determining the evolution stage in the biofilm formation.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials and Instruments

Sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄), glacial acetic acid, citric acid, monopotassium phosphate, boric acid, sodium hydroxide, cdGMP, guanosine (Guo), guanosine-5'-monophosphate disodic (GMP), N-butryryl L-homoserine lactone (C₄-HSL), N-hexyl L-homoserine lactone (C₆-HSL), N-decanoyl L-homoserine lactone (C₁₀-HSL), N-undecanoyl L-homoserine lactone (C₁₁-HSL), N-dodecanoyl L-homoserine lactone (C₁₂-HSL), N-3-oxo-dodecanoyl L-homoserine lactone (3-O-C₁₀-HSL), N-3-oxo-dodecanoyl L-homoserine lactone (3-O-C₁₂-HSL), 2-Heptyl-3-hydroxy-4(1H)-quinolone (PQS), pyocyanin (PYO), and enterobactin (ENT) were purchased from Sigma. All the reagents were of analytical purity.

The Britton–Robinson buffer (BRB) consisted of a mixture of 0.04 M boric acid, 0.04 M phosphoric acid, and 0.04 M acetic acid that has been titrated to the desired pH with 0.20 M sodium hydroxide.

The electrochemical measurements were performed on an Autolab PGSTAT 302N (Metrohm Autolab, The Netherlands) equipped with the associated Nova 1.10.4 software. All the SPEs were purchased from Metrohm Dropsens (Oviedo, Spain). Several working electrode materials were used: graphite (C-SPE), graphene (GPH-SPE), ordered mesoporous carbon (OMC-SPE), carbon nanotubes (CNT-SPE), and gold (Au-SPE).

All three bacterial strains were clinical isolates. *Escherichia coli* and *Proteus vulgaris* were isolated from calf fecal samples, while *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was isolated from cow milk.

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Sensor optimization

To determine the best electrode material for detecting cdGMP, cyclic voltammetry (CV) was used, with a potential window from -1.0 to +1.1 V. The scan rate ν was 0.05 V s⁻¹ and the step potential (E_{step}) was set at 0.00244 V. This method was also used to determine the electrochemical behavior of Guo and GMP molecules on CNT-SPE.

The most appropriate electrolyte for the oxidation of the molecule was determined by differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) analysis in different solvents. The potential window ranged from +0.1 to +1.3 V and the other parameters were set as follows: E_{step}=0.005 V, a modulation time of 0.025 s, and a modulation amplitude of 0.100 V.

2.2.2. Quantification method

To detect and quantify the target molecule, the DPV signal of the anodic peak of cdGMP was recorded. The analyte solution was initially prepared as a stock solution in ultrapure water and subsequently stored in a freezer to prevent degradation. Targeted concentrations were achieved by diluting the stock solution with acetate buffer 0.1 M, pH 4. The DPV parameters for the quantification method were the following: potential window from +0.4 to +1.2 V, ν 0.015 V s⁻¹, modulation amplitude 0.125 V and modulation time 0.010 s.

2.2.3. Interference studies

The selectivity of the method was tested towards the molecules that could be found together with cdGMP in the biofilm matrix. Several AIs molecules secreted by bacteria that are known to be good biofilm

Fig. 1. CVs of 10 μM cdGMP in 0.5 M H_2SO_4 on A. C-SPE, B. CNT-SPE, C. GPH-SPE, D. OMC-SPE. Inserts: focus on the specific range where the oxidation and reduction peaks are observed.

formers were tested for their interference with cdGMP. From this class, the molecules with homoserine lactone structure were selected, such as C₄-HSL, C₆-HSL, C₁₀-HSL, C₁₁-HSL, C₁₂-HSL, 3-O-C₁₀-HSL, and 3-O-C₁₂-HSL. PQS, the specific QS molecule for *P. aeruginosa* was also included in the study. Two virulence factors were also analyzed: PYO, specific for *P. aeruginosa* and ENT, a siderophore secreted by Gram-negative bacteria. The influence of these interferents was assessed by comparing the DPV signal of a 1 μM cdGMP solution both individually and in 1:1 combination with each interferent.

2.2.4. Analysis of laboratory biofilm samples

The developed sensor was used to investigate the concentrations of cdGMP in the biofilms formed after the cultivation of three distinct clinical strains of bacteria known for their biofilm-forming abilities: *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *P. vulgaris*. The biofilms were sampled and tested with the optimized method at different moments in their growth: 24, 48, and 72 h.

The bacterial biofilm cultivation within the wells, as well as its subsequent assessment, were adapted from various methodologies previously documented in the literature [25,26] and proceeded as follows: Suspensions of three to five colonies from each bacterial strain (*E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *P. vulgaris*) were prepared by adding them to 4 ml of nutrient broth, adjusted to a turbidity equivalent to 0.5 on the McFarland scale (corresponding to approximately 1.5×10^8 CFU ml^{-1}). Subsequently, 1 ml aliquots of this suspension were dispensed into three wells of the 12-well plate (with individual well dimensions of 22.1×17.5 mm and a culture area of 3.8 cm^2). At the same time, the control, consisting of sterile nutrient broth, was added to the remaining three

wells. Following inoculation, the plates were incubated at 37°C for a specific duration (24, 48, and 72 h). After incubation, the wells were subjected to a washing step (three times) with a 0.85% (w/v) NaCl solution to eliminate non-adherent bacterial cells. After this, the adherent bacterial populations were fixed using 1 ml of 100% methanol for 20 minutes. The plates were then dried at ambient temperature for 30 minutes prior to the addition of 1 ml of a 0.25% crystal violet solution, which was allowed to interact for 15 minutes. After removing the staining solution and washing with sterile distilled water, the plates were dried for an additional 30 minutes. Subsequently, 1 ml of pH 4 acetate buffer was introduced to each well and the entire biofilm adhering to the wells was carefully detached using a sterile loop. Finally, 200 μl of the biofilm suspension were measured at 450 nm using Bio-Rad PR3100 TSC Microplate Assay Testing to assess their optical density. The results were then compared to those obtained using the developed sensor.

For the DPV analyses conducted utilizing the sensor, in order to eliminate the influence of the matrix on the detection of cdGMP, the standard addition method was employed. A small volume of a standard cdGMP solution was added to the processed samples increasing the concentration of the solution with 250 nM, 500 nM, and 1000 nM in successive steps. The recovery was determined by extrapolating the calibration plot to zero.

Table 1

The peak potential/current intensity of the peaks and the standard deviation from 3 analyses observed from the CV analyses of 10 μM cdGMP in 0.5 M H_2SO_4 on different electrode materials (1st scan).

Electrode	Peak potential (V)	Current intensity (μA)
GPH-SPE	0.90	0.607 ± 0.107
OMC-SPE	0.91	2.171 ± 0.477
C-SPE	0.88	0.364 ± 0.023
CNT-SPE	0.89	0.635 ± 0.045

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Electrochemical behavior of cdGMP on different electrode materials

The electrochemical behavior of a solution containing 10 μM cdGMP was analyzed by conducting CV experiments on a wide potential window, from -1.0 to +1.1 V (Fig. 1). Different SPEs (C-SPE, CNT-SPE, GPH-SPE, OMC-SPE, and Au-SPE) were tested to determine the most suitable surface for cdGMP detection and to determine the benefits of modifying the working electrode surface with nanomaterials for the detection of the molecule of interest.

In all cases, the voltammograms showed multiple peaks in both oxidation and reduction. However, the majority of these peaks are

present both in the voltammograms of the molecule and the blank, except for the oxidation peak around +0.90 V, exclusively observed in the voltammograms corresponding to the analyte. This indicates that cdGMP exhibits a specific oxidation peak around +0.85 - +0.90 V on all four SPEs. At the second scan, the anodic peak corresponding to cdGMP decreases in height, indicating an irreversible oxidation of the molecule on all the tested surfaces. This electrochemical behavior has previously been observed in other guanine-derived molecules, such as deoxyguanosine (dGuo), GMP, and 2'-deoxyguanosine-5'-monophosphate (dGMP) [27].

The results showed that the smallest peak was obtained on C-SPE (Fig. 1A, Table 1). On the other hand, the SPEs that were modified with carbon nanomaterials displayed improved electrochemical properties, facilitating the efficient transfer of electrons to the electrode surface. This suggests that the modification of the electrode surface with nanomaterials can increase the sensitivity of the sensor.

When Au-SPE was tested (Fig. 2), DPV analysis showed an oxidation peak at approximately +0.95 V in the blank, corresponding to gold oxidation on the electrode surface. The peak height increased with successive analyses in the absence of cdGMP (Fig. 2A). The presence of this peak adversely impacted the detection of cdGMP, because of the overlapping of the two peaks (Fig. 2B).

While the signal obtained using OMC-SPE was the highest (Fig. 1D, Table 1), we decided to use the CNT-SPE (Fig. 1B) as the working surface

Fig. 2. DPV of 10 μM cdGMP in 0.5 mM H_2SO_4 on Au-SPE: A. successive analysis in blank and B. 1st scan in blank (black) and 10 μM cdGMP (red).

Fig. 3. The influence of pH and electrolyte on cdGMP detection: A. DPVs of 10 μM cdGMP in BRB at different pH values and B. DPVs of 10 μM cdGMP in different acidic solvents. For all analyses, a basic correction was performed using the moving average function.

Table 2

The peak potential/height of the peaks and the standard deviation from 3 analyses observed in DPV of a 10 μM solution of cdGMP in BRB at different pH values.

pH (BRB)	Peak	
	Peak potential (V)	Peak height (μA)
2	0.95	5.503 ± 0.156
3	0.93	4.904 ± 0.194
4	0.92	3.863 ± 0.149
5	0.91	3.541 ± 0.064
6	0.89	2.905 ± 0.012
7	0.86	2.777 ± 0.023
8	0.84	2.736 ± 0.049
9	0.78	2.491 ± 0.013
10	0.72	1.971 ± 0.019
11	0.65	1.357 ± 0.007
12	0.59	0.733 ± 0.018

Fig. 4. The electrochemical behavior of Guo, GMP, and cdGMP on CNT-SPE.

because it presented a high electrochemical signal, but also a very good reproducibility compared to OMC-SPE (Table 1).

3.2. Influence of the electrolyte and pH on the detection of cdGMP

To evaluate the impact of pH on the detection of cdGMP, we examined the DPV signal of the analyte across a range of pH values. The analyses were conducted on 10 μM solutions in BRB under varying pH conditions, from pH 2 to 12 (Fig. 3A).

The pH exerts an important impact on both the peak amplitude and peak potential (Fig. 3A), as both protons and electrons play important roles in determining the rate-controlling steps of the electrode reactions [27]. With the increase in pH, the peak potential undergoes a shift to a smaller value of the potential, concomitant with a reduction in peak height (Table 2).

Our study showed that the peak height is higher at acidic pH. Accordingly, four acidic electrolytes (H_2SO_4 0.5 M, BRB pH 2, acetate buffer 0.1 M pH 4 and 5) were studied to choose the optimal solvent for cdGMP detection (Fig. 3B). The best results were obtained in acetate buffer pH 4 and this medium was selected for the detection of cdGMP.

Previous studies that investigated the oxidation mechanism of dGMP have shown that the oxidation center of the molecule is the heterocycle, specifically the imidazole part [27]. The initial oxidation step of the molecule is believed to be a single electron removal leading to the formation of a cation radical. After the one-electron oxidation of GMP, rapid deprotonation occurs, leading to the formation of a neutral radical. This observation explains that the potential values are influenced by the pH level.

To investigate the oxidation mechanism of cdGMP, CV analyses were also conducted on 10 μM solutions of Guo and GMP in acetate buffer at pH 4. All three examined molecules exhibited an irreversible oxidation peak around +0.90 V (Fig. 4), confirming the fact that the oxidation center is the imidazole nucleus, common to the three molecules (Fig. 5).

This hypothesis is additionally confirmed by the fact that the height of the peak corresponding to cdGMP ($0.697 \pm 0.054 \mu\text{A}$) is almost two times higher than for GMP ($0.412 \pm 0.019 \mu\text{A}$), due to the presence of two imidazole nuclei in the structure of the cdGMP molecule.

The chemical structures of Guo, GMP, dGMP and cdGMP are presented in Fig. 5.

3.3. The optimization of the DPV parameters

To obtain a higher sensitivity, the electrochemical parameters of

Fig. 5. Chemical structures of A. Guo, B. GMP, C. dGMP and D. cdGMP.

Fig. 6. The influence of DPV parameters on cdGMP detection: **A.** DPVs of 10 μM cdGMP in acetate buffer pH 4 at different modulation amplitudes (modulation time=constant=0.025 s) and **B.** DPVs of 10 μM cdGMP in acetate buffer pH 4 at different modulation times (modulation amplitude=constant= 0.125 V). For all analyses, a basic correction was performed using the moving average function.

Table 3

The peak height observed in DPV of a 10 μM solution of cdGMP in acetate buffer pH, 4 after varying modulation amplitude and time.

Electrochemical parameter	Peak height
Modulation amplitude (V) (Modulation time=0.025 s)	0.025 0.626 ± 0.095
	0.050 2.250 ± 0.161
	0.075 3.983 ± 0.729
	0.100 4.880 ± 1.595
	0.125 5.361 ± 1.341
	0.150 5.009 ± 1.878
	0.175 4.559 ± 1.577
	0.200 3.523 ± 0.847
Modulation time (s) (Modulation amplitude=0.125 V)	0.010 12.343 ± 0.633
	0.015 9.278 ± 0.317
	0.020 6.558 ± 0.100
	0.025 5.082 ± 0.174
	0.030 4.231 ± 0.706
	0.035 3.534 ± 0.658
	0.040 2.608 ± 0.214
	0.050 1.670 ± 0.197

DPV (modulation time and modulation amplitude) were optimized for

the oxidation of cdGMP (Fig. 6). ν was kept constant for all analyses at 0.010 V s^{-1} .

An increase in the DPV signal is observed as the modulation amplitude increases up to 0.125 V; however, above this value, a decrease in the electrochemical signal becomes evident, indicating that a modulation amplitude of 0.125 V is optimal for the detection of cdGMP on CNT-SPE (Fig. 6A, Table 3).

When modulation time was varied, a heightened signal was noted as modulation time decreased, with a 3-fold increase in signal when modulation time was reduced from 0.030 s to 0.010 s (Fig. 6B, Table 3). Consequently, modulation time was set at 0.010 s for cdGMP detection.

3.4. Influence of the scan rate on the detection of cdGMP

CV was used to study the impact of ν on the anodic peak associated with cdGMP oxidation and to ascertain the electrochemical process on CNT-SPE (Fig. 7A). For each ν , the analyses were conducted in triplicate. The standard deviations are illustrated in red in Fig. 7B.

The current intensity (I_{pa}) of the oxidation peak exhibited a direct proportionality to ν . This relationship is expressed by the linear regression equation: $I_{pa} (\mu\text{A}) = 0.0106x + 0.3571$, with a correlation coefficient (R^2) of 0.9966 (Fig. 7B). This correlation suggests that the

Fig. 7. **A.** The evolution of the anodic peak of cdGMP with the change of ν for a 10 μM solution in acetate buffer pH 4 and **B.** The appropriate fittings of the peak currents for each ν , describing the oxidation process and the standard deviations for 3 determinations.

Fig. 8. The influence of the contact duration between a 10 μM cdGMP droplet and the CNT surface; Experimental conditions: DPV with potential window from +0.4 to +1.2 V, v 0.010 V s^{-1} , modulation amplitude 0.125 V and modulation time 0.010 s; Standard deviations for 3 determinations are indicated in red.

oxidation of cdGMP is governed by the adsorption of the molecule onto the CNT surface. This observation was confirmed by examining the impact of the contact duration between a 10 μM cdGMP drop and the electrode surface. The signal increased as the contact duration between the drop and the CNT surface extended (Fig. 8), suggesting that the adsorption of the molecule onto the electrode surface favored its oxidation. However, in order to simplify the analysis and shorten the analysis time, we decided to proceed with further studies without maintaining the sample droplet in contact with the electrode surface.

3.5. Calibration curve and limit of detection

Different concentrations of a standard solution of cdGMP (25 nM, 50 nM, 75 nM, 100 nM, 150 nM, 250 nM, 500 nM, 750 nM, and 1000 nM) were tested using the optimized method to address the analytical performance of the sensor. All the analyses were made in triplicate, revealing excellent reproducibility, with very small standard deviations (Fig. 9B).

The anodic peak around +0.85 V increased with the cdGMP concentration (Fig. 9A). A good linear relationship between the current height and the cdGMP concentration was observed in the 25 nM–1 μM

Fig. 9. A. The DPV analyses of cdGMP solutions at different concentrations and B. The linear fitting of the peak height and the concentration of cdGMP. Standard deviations for 3 determinations are indicated in red.

range (Fig. 9B).

The linear regression equation is: y (peak height) = 0.0045x ([cdGMP] (nM)) - 0.0096, $R^2 = 0.9998$

Table 4

Comparison of the developed sensor with other methods previously reported for cdGMP detection.

Method	Linear range	LOD	Samples	Ref
LC/ESI-MS/MS	0.025-10 nmol/run	0.050 nmol/run*	<i>Synechococcus elongatus</i>	[19]
BldD-based bimolecular fluorescence complementation sensor	–	2500 nM	<i>E. coli</i> , <i>S. Typhimurium</i> , and <i>S. enterica</i>	[16]
Fluorescent method based on aptamers	–	320 nM	–	[28]
Label-free electrochemical biosensor based on RNA riboswitch	50–1000 nM	50 nM	<i>E. coli</i>	[18]
Electrochemical sensor Based on CNT-SPE	25-1000 nM	15 nM	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>E. coli</i> , and <i>P. vulgaris</i>	This work

* Run refers to a 20 μl -volume injection

Abbreviations: LC/ESI-MS/MS, Liquid chromatography-electrospray ionization tandem mass spectrometry; BldD, the effector protein from *Streptomyces*

Fig. 10. Sensor selectivity for cdGMP detection.

Fig. 11. Interference with other electrochemically active substances.

The limit of detection (LOD) is 15 nM and was calculated with the following equation:

$$St \geq Sb + 3s$$

where St represents the analyte signal, Sb is the blank signal, and s is the standard deviation derived from five blank measurements.

Table 4 compares the analytical performance of the developed sensor with several other analytical methods for cdGMP detection in biofilm. Notably, the sensor developed in this study presents the widest dynamic range and the lowest LOD when compared to all other approaches. Additionally, the electrochemical sensor highlighted in this study exhibits several advantages compared to the other methods, including

simple and low-cost fabrication, a simple and rapid sensing process, and the capability for decentralized field-based sample analyses.

3.6. Interference studies

The selectivity of the sensor was evaluated concerning molecules potentially coexisting with cdGMP within the biofilm matrix. This specificity was examined by determining the electrochemical signal of cdGMP in the presence of other AI molecules (C₄-HSL, C₆-HSL, C₁₀-HSL, C₁₁-HSL, C₁₂-HSL, 3-O-C₁₀-HSL, and 3-O-C₁₂-HSL), a virulence factor from *P. aeruginosa* (PYO), and a siderophore specific to Gram-negative bacteria (ENT).

The DPV signal from a 1 µM cdGMP solution was compared with solutions containing both cdGMP and each interferent (1 µM). The sensor manifested pronounced selectivity in cdGMP detection, with negligible interference from the other biofilm-associated molecules (Fig. 10).

Under the specified conditions, ENT exhibited an oxidation peak at +0.20 V, while PQS displayed one at +0.18 V. However, the anodic peak of cdGMP was not affected by these molecules (Fig. 11). Although the method was primarily optimized for cdGMP detection, the interference study showed encouraging outcomes, indicating that the sensor might be adapted for the simultaneous detection of cdGMP, ENT, and PQS, thereby validating the biofilm formation.

3.7. Analysis of laboratory biofilm samples

The developed sensor was utilized to quantify cdGMP concentrations within biofilms grown in laboratory settings from three distinct clinical bacterial strains isolated from animals and recognized as good biofilm formers: *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *P. vulgaris*. The strains were sampled from cases of animal disease and not standard laboratory strains, and it is important to acknowledge the inherent limitations of cultivating biofilms in laboratory settings. These settings cannot fully replicate the

Fig. 12. Biofilm growth at 24 h, 48 h, 72 h and stained with crystal violet.

Fig. 13. Correlation between the concentration of cdGMP, determined by DPV analysis using the sensor, and the optical density of bacterial suspensions at 450 nm, measured at different incubation times. The cdGMP concentration (blue, left OY axis) and the optical density (purple, right OY axis) in the function of time (h) (OX axis): A. *E. coli*, B. *P. aeruginosa*, and C. *P. vulgaris*.

intricate dynamics and environmental conditions found in naturally occurring biofilms in the environment, industrial settings, or living organisms, but they offer valuable insights into fundamental processes underlying biofilm formation.

The biofilms were sampled and tested at various growth intervals, specifically 24, 48, and 72 h post-inoculation. The biofilm thickness was evaluated using the crystal violet staining technique (Fig. 12).

The DPV analyses were conducted in triplicate for each bacterial strain, at all three moments in the biofilm maturation and the standard deviations are illustrated in Fig. 13. The results demonstrated a positive relationship between biofilm thickness and the cdGMP concentrations as detected by the sensor. This emphasizes the sensor efficacy in discerning biofilm formation across different substrates.

To confirm biofilm formation and to validate the effectiveness of the sensor in the detection of cdGMP from real biofilm samples, the optical density of the biofilm suspensions was analyzed in triplicate at 450 nm in all three moments of biofilm sample collection.

Various factors can influence the growth patterns of bacterial biofilms, resulting in unique dynamics in biofilm development [2]. Our findings support these observations, highlighting distinct trends throughout biofilm formation stages (Fig. 13). A common trend in the biofilms formed by *P. aeruginosa* and *P. vulgaris* was observed, with an increase in biofilm growth from 24 to 48 h followed by a decrease at 72 h (Fig. 13B and C). Several reasons may explain this pattern. For example, biofilm development typically involves stages of attachment, maturation, and eventual detachment. The initial attachment stage occurs within a day [4], followed by the maturation phase, during which the

biomass of the biofilm increases significantly. In the later stages, biofilms reach a mature state, and some cells may detach or disperse, leading to a reduction in overall biofilm biomass. Furthermore, as the biofilm matures, the nutrient availability within it may become limited. This, coupled with potentially stressful conditions, can precipitate the death of bacterial cells. Collectively, these factors could contribute to a decline in biofilm biomass over time [2,4].

For the *E. coli* strain, a different growth pattern was described: a decrease at 48 h incubation followed by an increase at 72 h incubation (Fig. 13A). Apart from potential inconsistencies in the inoculation procedure specific to the *E. coli* well at 48 h or during sample processing, this pattern may be related to the natural maturation process of biofilms. As biofilms mature, cells produce extracellular polymeric substances (EPS), reinforcing the biofilm structure [2]. The biofilm might strengthen as it matures from 24 to 72 h, and this process might not be as pronounced at 48 h.

After quantifying the concentration of cdGMP in biofilm samples using the developed sensor, a consistent correlation between the cdGMP concentration and the optical density of bacterial suspensions was observed across all three bacterial strains (Fig. 13). The variations in cdGMP concentration over time were in direct accordance with the growth patterns previously outlined for each strain.

These results confirm the effectiveness of the developed sensor in biofilm detection and indicate that cdGMP concentration may offer important information about the evolution stage in biofilm development, especially for Gram-negative bacteria.

The advantages of electrochemical sensors, such as portability and

ease of use, synergize with the increased sensitivity and selectivity of the developed sensor, allowing the detection of bacterial biofilm in decentralized analyses in the hospital environment or industries affected by biofilm.

4. Conclusions

The fast, selective, and sensitive electrochemical detection of cdGMP, a molecule present in the bacterial biofilm, was achieved using commercially available SPEs modified with CNTs. The optimized sensor showed excellent sensitivity (25 nM – 1 μM linear range, LOD of 15 nM) and selectivity (low interference from other molecules present in the biofilm). The sensor was successfully applied to the quantification of cdGMP concentrations within biofilms grown in the laboratory from three distinct bacterial strains recognized as good biofilm formers: *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *P. vulgaris*. For all three bacteria it was observed a correlation between the concentration of cdGMP and the formation and evolution of the biofilm, confirming that the developed sensor can be used for the detection of the bacterial biofilm and to determine its evolution stage. While well-based cultivation systems may not fully reflect the complexity of biofilms grown in flow cells or encountered in real-world settings, they can serve as a useful tool for hypothesis testing and preliminary experimentation. This study paves the way for the rapid, affordable, easy-to-use *in situ* detection of the biofilm formed by Gram-negative bacteria in a variety of environments.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Cecilia Cristea reports financial support was provided by European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under the grant agreement "European integration of new technologies and social-economic solutions for increasing consumer trust and engagement in seafood products" (Fish-EuTrust), Grant Agreement: 101060712/2022. D.C. thanks the Iuliu Hatieganu UMF internal grant no. 649/4/11.01.2024.

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